

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INTERPRETATION OF "TEACHING STRATEGIES BLOCK ELEMENTS" BASED ON THE "SYSTEM-STRUCTURE" APPROACH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8130356>

Abstract

In the article, it is emphasized that the curriculum reform is conditioned by the need to ensure the adequacy of the implementation of education to the challenges of the 21st century, to cultivate a creative, self-developing personality, and the content of the abilities that must be transformed into the subject of a student who has completed his general education is shown.

The significance of the educator's reference to the "system-structure" approach in the research work both in familiarizing himself with the essence of the "General education program" and in his practical activities related to its implementation, the relevance of the subject-oriented curricula to the content of the science field, and its perfect system of concepts, are directly related to these concepts. It is drawn to the center of attention directed to its absorption.

In the article, 1) the principles of the pedagogical process, 2) planning of training on the subject, 3) the forms and methods used in the organization of training, 4) the content standards, which are included in the "Teaching strategies" block of the "block-scheme" form of the structure of the foreign language subject curriculum at the general education level.

Keywords: subject curriculum, learning strategies, completeness, unit of study, research question.

Relevance of the research topic.

Observations show that mistakes are made in the activities of educators in the application of the curriculum of foreign language subjects at the general education level. This has a negative effect on the level of efficiency of the foreign language teaching process.

It is undeniable that the level of understanding of any real existence (objective existence) has a determining effect on the results of using it in adequate directions. Based on our scientific observations over the past ten years (at the stage of applying a new approach to the philosophy of general education in Azerbaijan), we have come to the conclusion that in the process of using subject curricula (including foreign language subject curriculum), the basis of the errors manifested in the activities of educators in the process of using subject curricula (including foreign language subject curriculum) is based on a number of reasons, as well as subject the essence of the curriculum is not sufficiently honestly understood by these subjects. Based on our experience of scientific activity, we claim that the "system-structure" approach (the idea of L. Bertalanf [14;8], which is the basis of system analysis) is the most reliable dialectical method of understanding any objective reality (material or spiritual) and getting to its essence. In other words, it is a way of spiritual awakening (it is essentially a form of cognitive movement). The analysis of the materials we have collected gives reason to say that this method is insufficiently used in the theoretical and technological directions of revealing the essence of the foreign language subject curriculum and determining the ways of its application. Therefore, we recommend that only one of the many issues aimed at

solving the problem that created the basis for the manifestation of the above-mentioned error - "Interpretation of the "Teaching strategies" block elements" of the foreign language subject curriculum at the general education level on the basis of the "system-structure" approach" and its actual research we claim to be the subject.

Interpretation of generalizations formed on the basis of research materials.

It is known that "in the 21st century, the main value in the life and development of both society and each of its members is a creative, self-developing personality." [15; 16] and there is also the fact that education cannot exist outside the realities of a changing world. [11]

Therefore, since the main value in the modern period is a creative, self-developing personality, the educational process should form creativity and self-development abilities in the child. This, in turn, is based on the following activity, the need to understand and the abilities: 1) logical thinking; 2) critical approach to objects and events of the surrounding world; 3) independent decision-making; 4) change what is around at a creative speed; 5) independent acquisition of knowledge; 6) solving practical problems; 7) setting new goals for personality development.

Despite what has been said, a student who has completed general education should be able to: analyze the texts of different styles and genres that he listens to and reads, convey their content to someone else in a concise and partly extensive form; to use monologue and dialogue forms of speech; preparing a plan, thesis, overview, project, opinion; to logically justify their

ideas through examples and evidence, to summarize the main points expressed in different ideas; perform calculations and programming, use mathematical language, build algorithms, make assumptions; to use the methods and means of observation, measurement, calculation, experiment, evaluation to understand the surrounding world; to explain the nature of the basic regularities in nature and their interrelation; to compare, classify and present various facts, opinions and evidence; independently perform tasks that require creativity in the training process; to use different sources of information to perform training tasks; to consciously determine one's capabilities, inclination and interest, to demonstrate voluntary and involuntary qualities; to evaluate the results of his work; to follow public behavior, as well as relevant safety and medical-hygiene rules, healthy lifestyle norms; to demonstrate that he has national, moral, legal, aesthetic values, citizenship position, and leadership qualities; to work together in solving problems, to evaluate the performance of oneself and others in the collective work process; to communicate in a foreign language and so on.

The listed skills of the student who has completed his general education - the general learning results are formed as a synthesis and dialectical unification of the results targeted in the teaching process of all subjects taught in general education schools.

"Revealing the child's creative abilities and realizing them, creating favorable conditions for the formation of his personality is one of the main goals of education". [7; 290-292] There is no doubt that subjects, which are the main enabling components of the implementation of general education, are of high value as an important tool in the formation of the personality of schoolchildren. The "enabling" functions of the subjects are expressed in the "Education Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan" in the following content:

- ensures that students are taught the basics of science, inculcated the necessary knowledge, skills and habits, prepare them for life and work;

- enables physical and intellectual development of students, acquisition of necessary knowledge, formation of civic thinking based on healthy lifestyle and civilized values, inculcation of respect for national and worldly values, determination of rights and responsibilities in front of family, society, state and environment. [2;21-23]

Based on the official state documents, we can say that "the content of general education subjects aims at the following hierarchical goals by dividing them into different levels of education":

- to inculcate reading, writing and calculation skills in primary education, to form basic knowledge about man, society and nature, elements of logical thinking, aesthetic, artistic taste and other characteristics;

- oral speech and writing culture, communication skills, cognitive activity, the development of logical thinking, the formation of relevant knowledge and ideas about the subjects included in the educational program as well as the development of world civilization,

the ability to use modern information and communication tools, events to provide the ability to evaluate and determine their own future directions of action;

- realization of talents and abilities, preparation for independent life and professional choice, formation of an active citizen position, respect for national and universal values, human rights and freedoms and tolerance, free use of modern information and communication technologies and other technical means, acquiring the basics of economic knowledge, communicating in one or more foreign languages, etc. ensure. (for more information, see:[2])

In the mentioned system of knowledge, skills and habits, what is obtained at different educational levels during the teaching of a foreign language is included as a component, which can be interpreted as follows:

At the level of primary education, listening comprehension, oral speech, formation of initial writing skills, creation and development of correct reading skills are ensured.

By taking the development of oral speech as the main requirement at the secondary education level, the formation of students' communication skills, enrichment of vocabulary, mastering of the most necessary grammatical concepts and language constructions, development of reading, writing techniques and written speech, and listening comprehension skills are ensured.

By developing the activities intended for the full secondary education level, students acquire communicative skills and culture of communication in a foreign language, enrich their vocabulary, arouse interest in learning a foreign language in depth, and expand their worldviews based on familiarity with the country (countries) in which they learn the language. Taking into account all the circumstances, the main goal of foreign language education in secondary schools is defined as the formation of speech, language and communicative skills and habits. In order to achieve the goal we explained, it is necessary to carry out the following tasks: students' acquisition of important linguistic (phonetic, orthographic, lexical, etc.) knowledge; acquainting students with the culture and traditions of the countries where the language is studied, forming their ability to represent their country and its culture in a foreign language and intercultural environment; development of communicative skills in speech activity; formation and development of language perception, all types of memory, logical, critical and creative thinking (analysis, comparison, generalization, drawing conclusions, etc.); education of citizenship qualities, respect for other cultures.

In our opinion, it is of particular importance that the subject teacher (as well as the foreign language teacher) honestly knows the tasks set before the general education (general expected results). This is necessary to put the activity related to the educational process into a result-oriented system.

As is known, the goal is a system-creative component in all processes, as well as in training activities. At the same time, in order to achieve the goal (otherwise, the result will not be achieved), it is very important to implement the training process in what content, based on which strategy, and based on which assessment

mechanisms. "The new necessary minimum of training at the levels of general education, the knowledge threshold, the general training results for the subject and the training results that will be obtained in advance of the acquired skills at individual levels of general education (subsystems of the implementation system of general education) (which these results are in the expected general results contained as components - italics are ours) is considered one of the most important problems of education". [12;71]

As is known, the teacher should be able to find both theoretical and practical answers to all questions related to the learning process. He should know which model he uses in the process of which he is a facilitator and what specific features this model has. This model incorporates the superior merits of traditional models (it should not be forgotten that innovation is not a complete denial of the old, such a denial can bring more harm than good) and what success it promises to the real pedagogical process.

Based on what we have said, we summarize that currently applied in general education schools "perceived as a conceptual document that enables efficient organization, purposeful and consistent implementation of all activities related to the educational process" [8; 228-229] it would be beneficial for the general work to interpret the main features of the educational program (curriculum) based on the "system-structure" approach.

The teacher is one of the subjects of the "enabling function" in the implementation of the educational program. The level of his penetration into the essence of the mentioned program has a conditioning effect on the effectiveness of its activity. Therefore, it is important to refer to the "system-structure" approach both in familiarization with the essence of the program and in the practical activities related to its implementation, which brings us to this conclusion by the analysis of research materials and our work experience.

It should be emphasized here that the essence of the system is determined by its structure and function, that is, by the nature of the relationship between the elements and their behavior, and by the specificity of the relationship between the object and the conditions. Without studying the elements that make up the system and their interaction, it is impossible to distinguish the continuous, important and necessary relationships here. Such continuous, important and necessary interaction of elements characterizes the structure of the system. The law of relationships of structural elements acts as an invariant of the system. Without learning and opening the relationship of the elements with the whole formed by them, both the function of the system and the functions of each element with regard to the whole remain in the shadows. The full concept is understood in terms of the system, it is the organization of the system.

Each system has its own structure and the function that this structure carries. A system can be viewed as a whole consisting of the unity of its structure and function. Systems differ from each other not only by their structure and functions, but also mainly by the nature of the unity of structure and function, the nature of this unity.

The educational program (curriculum) determines the content of education and the rules of mastering it at different levels and levels of education in accordance with the state educational standards. [9; 106-107] The educational program includes the curriculum, educational programs for subjects, recommendations on methodical provision, assessment and other relevant educational technologies. [8;173] Listed are subsystems of the Education program - complete.

The foreign language subject curriculum includes a balanced and comprehensive approach that involves the learning of various skills; enables achievement of content standards using active learning methods; implies constant assessment of students' knowledge and understanding, making corrections during the academic year; ensures involvement of students in training, preparation and motivation for continuous education; it envisages the use of modern technologies when students are studying, evaluating their knowledge, and increasing their literacy; has adequate training resources and administrative support. [4;158-161] The block diagram form of the structure of the mentioned curriculum can be drawn as follows: [8; 38] (see Scheme 1)

The "Teaching strategies" block covers the forms, methods and techniques used by the teacher in the teaching process. It should be noted that until this time, the concept of "educational strategies" was not used in the Azerbaijani pedagogical literature. However, recently, during the period of educational reform, the concept of "educational strategy" has started to be applied when preparing subject curricula. [5; 280] Developing the concept of learning strategies in new subject curricula and using it more effectively in organizing the pedagogical process requires, first of all, an explanation of education as one of the main pedagogical concepts in terms of modern requirements. The "Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Education" states that education is the process of systematized (according to the interests of the state, society, individual - italics are ours) acquisition of knowledge, skills, habits and its result. [2; 6] It is emphasized in scientific sources that education should be treated not only as a result or just a process, but as a way of expression with broader shades of meaning. "Especially the personality-oriented nature of education requires to approach it from several positions: education is a value; education is a system; education is a process; education is the result". [13;115] We fully agree with this opinion.

Scheme 1

First of all, education is viewed as a value that includes language, mentality, national skills and traditions. In the formation of these values, personality orientation, culture, collectivism, systematicity, and integrity act as leading principles. Education, which has its own system, exists in stages. These stages, which differ in their expected results, complement each other and form a general system of education by being sequentially arranged. At this time, democratization, humanization, differentiation, individualization, socialization, diversity and inclusion play a key role as leading principles. Education is also treated as a process, since it continuously encompasses the acquisition of universal and national values in the process of socialization. Its didactic basis is relevance to nature, practicality, orientation, variability, gradation, consideration of individual needs and continuity. Since education is the conclusion of teacher and student activities as a whole, it is viewed as a result. It is evaluated as the end of a whole step-by-step process. [5; 280]

Among the elements contained in the "Education strategies" block, "Description of the main requirements for the organization of training on the subject" has a special place. It is necessary to follow the important requirements - didactic principles in the proper construction of the pedagogical process. In the organization of the pedagogical process in accordance with the currently applied curricula in the general education system, it is considered necessary to take principles such as 1) completeness of the pedagogical process, 2) creation of equal opportunities in training, 3) student orientation, 4) development orientation, 5) stimulation of activity, 6) creation of a supportive environment.

Among the elements contained in the "Teaching strategies" block, "Teaching planning by subject" has a special place. Creating annual planning is the most important task facing educators. Planning is the direction of action of teachers to determine the main goals and

achieve them. The annual planning shows when and in what order the teaching unit will teach.

In scientific sources, it is recommended to expect the following sequence of subject planning: 1. To determine the educational units to be implemented based on the content standards; 2. Determine the principle of sequence of teaching units; 3. Allocate time according to the curriculum for each educational unit; 4. Taking into account student interests in each case. [5; 281]

The main documents used in the annual planning process are: content standards; assessment standards; education plan; textbook; methodological tool for the teacher. In particular, let us emphasize that during the preparation of the calendar plan, the weeks of the school year, important events that will take place in the school year (historical days), the name of the study units and the subjects included in them are determined. The content standards (sub-standards) to be realized through each teaching unit and topic are selected, the sources (resources) to be used are determined, and the time allocated for each topic is noted. Based on the model annual planning, the teacher individually prepares a daily or weekly lesson plan.

According to the descriptive scheme of the curriculum of the subject, in the "Education strategies" block, the "element acting as a central link" is the form and methods (methods) of the organization of education.

Despite the fact that the clear understanding of the concept of "Teaching method", which is one of the important elements of the "Teaching strategies" system, and the discovery of its essence, have important theoretical and practical importance, debates among didacts in this direction have been going on for a long time. [11] In our opinion, the training method is a system of rules aimed at solving the educational, educational and developmental tasks set in the training process, determined by the principles derived from the regularities of

training, and ensuring the dialectical unity of the activities of teachers and students (a component of the training process).

Since the standards are result-oriented and student-oriented, it is considered appropriate to use active learning methods in their implementation. The characteristic features of active learning methods include: 1) Attention is focused primarily on the formation of the student's personality; 2) The teacher acts as a coordinator of educational activities, a consultant and assistant of students; 3) Students become active researchers in the process of problem solving; 4) Knowledge and skills are acquired independently by students; 5) There are conditions for cooperation between teacher - student, student - student; 6) The integrative organization of lessons is preferred; 7) The application of non-standard lessons is given wide scope. [5; 286-287]

Training practice has confirmed that the main organizational form of training and education work in secondary schools is the lesson. A lesson is a part or cell of the pedagogical process that has been completed to one degree or another. (academician M. Mehdizadeh)

The improvement of educational material, which contains a part of human social experience, and educational methods aimed at its mastery, conditions the modernization of their form of existence (educational material and methods for the lesson act together in the place of content) (turning into a suitable way of existence) (such is the dialectical dependence between form and content). Therefore, in addition to "traditional lesson", "modern lesson", "developing lesson", "problematic lesson", "phased lesson", "synthetic lesson", "active lesson" etc. Concepts reflecting the quality characteristics of the lesson were used from time to time, and scientific comments were given to them. The "modern lesson" model was created with intense pedagogical, psychological, and methodological research and was formed according to the features and challenges of the era (the current century, time period).

In the concept of "modern lesson", the word "modern" has a unique heuristic meaning. "Modern lesson" does not mean "today's lesson". A lesson based on the successes of the time is called a modern lesson. In this sense, they usually distinguish two aspects that are organically connected with each other. Often, when they say modern lesson, they understand it only as raising the scientific-theoretical level of the lesson, modernizing it. The lesson should reflect the achievements of the time according to its scientific and theoretical level. This is without a doubt. However, it would be one-sided to explain the meaning of the modern lesson only in this root. We are talking about a pedagogical phenomenon. The word "modern" characterizes the lesson. This is true both from a psychological and pedagogical point of view, as well as from a linguistic point of view. The lesson becomes modern not only due to its scientific-theoretical level, but also due to its pedagogical concept - it is built with new dimensions of pedagogical thinking. [7; 36-37]

The analysis of materials obtained from pedagogical sources leads us to the conclusion that the use of

the concept of "modern lesson" is ambiguously accepted by pedagogical researchers (theorists) and practitioners: it is more important to talk about the changes in the requirements of the lesson, its construction in accordance with the modern tasks of the school, and the use of appropriate terminology. preferred.

The lesson as an organizational form of training is still being effectively researched, its types and structure are being clarified, the theory and practice of organizing and managing the learning material at the level that can play the role of the form of procedural movement is being worked out, in short, this problem has an eternal nature. We share the claim that the optimality of the structure of the lesson mainly depends on the consideration of the following factors: a) the content of the training material; b) didactic goals and tasks; c) methods and tasks of training; ç) age and personal characteristics of students; d) level of students' ability to learn.

The attitude of the student to the content and tools of the training material can be manifested as stationary or problematic. Therefore, depending on the stationarity or problem, the student's thought movement is reproductive or productive in nature. In the forms of organization of training, the content of the training material and the methods of action adequate to it appear in the place of the content. Therefore, the substructures of the forms of organization of training and their relationship remain in the monopoly of the relationship between the student's analytical and heuristic activities. The basis of the pedagogical (external), mental (internal) and methodical inter-structural relations of the organizational form is also the relation between the students' analytical and heuristic activities. The relationship between the degree of pedagogical influence in the training process and the student's internal activity and independence reflects the nature of his (student's) activity. At present, the approach to this process as a field of activity aimed at developing the human personality has begun to dominate. This did not remain unaffected by the forms of education, views on its organization, and directions for improvement. In our modern time, the idea of active (interactive) learning has gained a superior position due to the above-mentioned effects. By the way, let's emphasize that "modern lesson" is used as a synonym for the concept of "active lesson", which is an organizational form of active (interactive) training.

The paradigms of the lesson, which is the organizational form of that model (the way of implementing education), are: approach to students as subjects; dialogic approach; existentiality (consideration of the integrity of human nature); integrativeness; providing a developmental character; formation of pedagogical personnel at a level that meets modern requirements; the fundamentality of the teaching-learning process: the character of the training is "subject-subject" ("S-S"); activity of the participants during the whole lesson; creation of a problem situation at the beginning of the lesson and directing its progress to the solution of the problem; conducting the lesson in the form of research; directing students to independent discovery of new knowledge through thought-provoking and guiding questions; conducting the lesson in the form of dialogue; regular existence of mutual cooperation and

feedback between teachers and students; wide use of group work, joint activity of students; diversity and innovation of learning tools and tasks; use of worksheets; creative application of knowledge, etc.

Among the elements included in the structure of the lesson, which is the main organizational form of active (interactive) training, are: 1) Motivation (posing a problem, putting forward hypotheses); 2) Conducting research (searching for facts to test hypotheses); 3) Information exchange (presentation of obtained data and student research); 4) Discussion and organization of information (discussion of obtained information, connection of various facts, their systematization); 5) Summarizing and drawing conclusions (generalizations, comparison of results with hypotheses and conclusion about their confirmation or refutation, answer to the research question); 6) Productive (creative) application (application in new conditions, solving practical problems); 7) Evaluation or reflection (inspection and evaluation of personal activity - this can be done at any stage).

The structure of the active lesson reminds of the stages of the research process (the main shade of the learning process is research). In an active lesson, new information is obtained through the student himself (as a result of research). The stage of application in an active lesson is creative in nature. One of the special stages of the active lesson is the reflection stage. As a result of reflection, the student understands the main stages of his research activity.

Learning success is determined not only by the student's ability to learn, overall abilities, etc., but also by learning motivation. In other words, for him to "read well", along with all other conditions, it is necessary to form learning motivation.

Motivation is an important component in an active lesson - it is a process that activates the thinking process and stimulates the cognitive activity of students. The existence of this process is determined by components such as goal, need, personal meaning, motive.

The motivation phase consists of the following parts: a question or task is formulated to pose the problem; questions are suggested; assumptions are made.

Among the factors that create motivation are the following: the problem situation that creates various hypotheses; properties of the object (unusuality, free thinking and interest-generating feature); availability of research opportunities; the possibility of creativity. [10;258] Motivation is mainly based on two principles: 1) problematic; 2) purposefulness. Motivation should be consistent with the learning outcomes of the lesson. Before establishing the motivation, the sub-standards and then the learning outcomes of the lesson should be determined. The research question arises as a result of the motivation. Motivation can be short and gradual. A short motivation consists of only one research question. Staged motivation includes at least two stages.

Guiding questions, tasks are focused on learning outcomes, influencing factors are further strengthened for students to become active carriers of the lesson. To formulate a research question, the teacher must first identify the summary at the end of the lesson. The motivational phase ends with the hypotheses put forward

according to the research question. It is important to return to it at the end of the lesson. As a result of motivation, the research question should serve the learning outcomes. In this process, the topic of the lesson plays only the role of a tool. Although the topic is a tool, in certain cases it can influence the content of the motivation.

In scientific sources [15] it is emphasized that all possible ways of creating motivation are divided into three main groups, which we also appreciate this consideration: interpretation of symbolic (symbolic) material (when the teacher presents this material, the teacher offers students to answer the following questions: "What does this mean?" "?", "How does this relate to the topic we are studying?"); encouragement to ask questions.

The following criteria are used to evaluate motivation: appropriateness of motivation; the emergence of problems and various hypotheses as a result of motivation; Conciseness of motivation, implementation in a short time; that the teacher spends little time and effort on its preparation; understanding by children with moderate difficulty (taking into account their age and knowledge level).

The purpose of "Information exchange", one of the concluding stages of the active lesson, is to familiarize all students with new facts and findings. Information sharing can only be effective if the class is focused on active listening and feedback.

The purpose of the "Discussion and organization of information" stage is to systematize knowledge based on new facts and reveal the main relationship to find an answer to the research question. It is clear that the material that the teacher has to work with is detailed. He must try to connect these scattered facts to discover the main unifying idea and pattern. In that time period, comparison, analysis and synthesis are used. "How to group all these facts?" - in order for the students to be able to answer the question, the teacher should be able to imagine in advance how information can be compared, organized and reconstructed, with the help of which criteria. Let us emphasize that the choice here depends on the content of the material and the purpose of the research.

"Deriving conclusions, justifying generalization" is one of the structural elements of the lesson. After generalization, the idea formed should be compared with the research question (Does it answer this question?) and with the initial hypotheses (Are any of these correct?).

In the implementation of the foreign language subject curriculum, daily planning for each active lesson system is also an element to be focused on. It is useful to include the following in the daily planning: determine the expected results of the lesson (determine the learning results of the lesson based on the sub-standard); determine what conclusions (generalizations) students will reach at the end of the lesson; preparing the motivation of the lesson (creating a problem situation, choosing the type of motivation, setting the research question correctly); identify sources of knowledge used to collect new knowledge during research; develop research tasks that can lead to defined expected results;

determining research methods; prepare the necessary materials and worksheets, determine the presentation form of the research; express guiding questions used during the discussion; systematization of information (scheme, formula, graph, table, project, etc.); preparing additional information, tasks, taking into account the assumed new results; determine the time for each phase of the lesson; prepare tasks for the creative application phase of the lesson; choose the evaluation form (method), define the criteria; determining the course of reflection based on the needs of teachers and students; determine the technical means that will be used in the lesson; prepare stationery to be used in the lesson. [5; 286]

Individual, pair, large and small group work is included among the forms of organization of students' educational activities (work forms) included in the "Teaching strategies" block. Work with small groups and pairs are considered active forms of learning. In the course of the lesson, during the work in pairs, students work in pairs, they work together in the performance of training tasks. This allows them to better understand each other and realize their responsibilities. During the work with small groups, students (3-6 people) unite in small groups and are involved in joint activities to solve any problem. Group work allows students to express their opinions and listen to others, evaluate their own and others' work. In addition, they get the idea that there are different views and approaches on the same issue.

During the organization of group work, the teacher's and students' adherence to certain rules has a positive effect on the effectiveness of the work, which are presented in scientific sources in the following aspects:

1. Aspects related to the teacher's organizational activity: 1) Accurately measuring the organization of the work: determining the goals, plan and duration of the work; 2) prepare necessary materials for group work (tasks for group work, worksheets, etc.); 3) Pre-determine the method of dividing into groups according to the objectives of the lesson; 4) Divide and place participants into groups; 5) Correctly divide the duties of group members; 6) Provide accurate information on the performance of the work and write it on the board (or other means); 7) To define (or remember) the rules of group work; 8) Create conditions for the exchange stage of group work results; 9) Bringing the evaluation criterion to the attention of the participants.

2. Aspects related to the teacher's behavioral activity. 1) To determine and control the work of groups; 2) If necessary, to intervene in the work of students, to detect problems arising in the process of group work in a timely manner, and to provide assistance in solving those problems; 3) Asking guiding questions to students, directing them to search; 4) Answering students' questions, paying more attention to weak students; 5) Answering the questions of group members, helping those who have difficulties; 6) Note the positive and negative aspects of students' and group work progress and discuss it during evaluation.

The following are attributed to the organizational aspects of group work by students: 1) correctly dividing the tasks of group members; 2) correctly identify group leaders; 3) to use time effectively. Behavioral aspects

of group work are attributed by students: 1) to be active during group work; 2) fulfill the obligation and take responsibility for one's own behavior; 3) listen carefully to each other, work together, cooperate, help and support each other; 4) collectively help the group to successfully achieve its goals; 5) to express one's point of view; 6) respect each other's ideas; 7) to confirm their thoughts and ideas with knowledge (facts); 8) to help create an environment of good relations, not to allow personal criticism, negative comments and insults; 9) not to allow conflict, to compete in the positive sense of the word; 10) looking for compromise ways when solving the problem; 11) not to allow extraneous conversations, talk on the topic given by the teacher; 12) observe discipline during work; 13) obey the rules of group work. (For details see: [10;15])

It is useful for the teacher, which is the main component of active/interactive training, which we consider as a subsystem of the perfect training system, to expect the following facilitation rules in the implementation of the guidance position as his specific function.

1. The following rules are expected for the purpose of inciting thought: 1) involving students in determining the subject of the lesson during the motivation phase; 2) to include tasks that develop students' logical, critical, creative thinking and scientific-research habits in the lesson; 3) use more open questions; 4) to use concrete material, comparison and contrast, analogy methods during facilitation; 5) use guiding questions that are close in meaning; 6) not to express the word or idea that the participant (student) could say instead; 7) determine the main idea contained in the material and work on students' generalization skills; 8) not to allow the students' answers to be formally heard, to summarize the main ideas of the students; 9) clarifying students' answers during facilitation.

2. Information provision rules refer to: 1) starting the facilitation and checking that the students have the necessary knowledge; 2) to use not only the materials in the textbook, but also various documents, problem and example books, informational literature, students' own experiences and observations in the lesson; 3) Apply different ways of understanding the material; 4) to say the questions and answers as short as possible, concisely and according to the level of the students; 5) to clarify in time the new concepts presented by other students, as well as the misunderstanding of the question or reasoning.

3. Organizational support rules include: 1) when organizing the discussion, conveying to all students that everyone's opinion can be important for gaining new knowledge; 2) form students' ability to plan and organize their activities; 3) record the main cases identified during group work on the board or on paper; 4) to offer special signs to students to express their approval or displeasure; 5) to prevent attempts aimed at disrupting the environment of business activity, inappropriate or inappropriate conversations, for this, by stopping the student politely, reminding him of the order to convey his thoughts briefly and meaningfully. [10; 255]

It should be noted that facilitation is the cooperation of teachers and students, mutual respect and trust, acceptance of students as they are and their constant

support by the teacher; confidence in students' abilities, stimulation of thinking; it is based on the creation of learning stimulus and motivation in students, their adaptation to the classroom environment, and the special sensitive attitude of the teacher. It should be accepted that facilitation is the process of organizing, activating and effectively directing the discussion in the group; the feature of the facilitation process is that the information is not delivered by the facilitator, but by the group; the position of the facilitator, its main function is to provoke thought and direct it in the necessary direction; the facilitation approach is to focus on the full satisfaction of cognitive and creative needs, that is, on students realizing their abilities; The teacher-facilitator plays the role of a guide in the process of acquiring knowledge by the child.

The document containing the interpretation of the content standards is one of the important elements included in the "Teaching strategies" block. Scientific sources emphasize that the content standard is a state requirement set by the state for the level of knowledge and skills of the student. [5;468] The subject standards cover the content that is important for all students within the secondary education course, describe the students' comprehension abilities, knowledge and skills, determine the issues that every student in the country can and should study in the subject, and prepare students for the next level of secondary education.

The new approach to setting the content of the standards envisages that each standard consists of several defined objectives (sub-standards) and is repeated throughout the grades in an appropriately expanding capacity.

The content standards of this or that subject are systematized by classes and represented by the content line. The objective of each standard includes several expected learning outcomes defined according to the primary, secondary and upper secondary levels of education. A balance of abilities such as basic computational and procedural skills, cognitive understanding, and problem solving is expected when setting standards. These three components of the teaching and mastering of the relevant subject are not isolated from each other, they must be connected to each other and complement each other.

The function of the core standard is to explain the defined learning outcomes in a general way along the content lines. It is attributed to the functions of the sub-standards: it creates a reliable basis for the precise determination of learning objectives; plays an important role in the correct selection of training strategies; ensures integration in training; ensures continuous development of training content; provides summative assessment for classes and subjects.

Scientific novelty and theoretical significance of the research work.

1) The importance of the application of the "system-structure" approach method, which was formed as an important branch of the dialectic of the subject curriculum (specifically, the discovery of the essence of the foreign language curriculum and the determination of its application methods), was brought to the attention of researchers; 2) The discovery of the essence of the

foreign language subject curriculum at the general education level and its The solution of one of the cognitive issues that determines the solution of the problem of processing the application in the optimal version - the interpretation of the elements of the "Training strategies block" based on the "system-structure" approach" was presented.

Practical significance of the research work.

We hope that the solution of one of the important cognitive issues that determines the solution to the problem of uncovering the essence of this or that subject curriculum (as well as the foreign language subject curriculum) applied at the general education level and its application in the optimal version - the "system-structure" approach of the "Elements of the Learning Strategies Block" the introduction of "based on interpretation" will have a positive effect on the formation of the environment for the elimination of errors manifested in the activities of educators in the application of the foreign language subject curriculum.

The result.

1) The level of understanding of any real thing (objective existence) has a determining effect on the results of using it in adequate directions. 2) making mistakes in the activities of educators in the application of any subject curriculum (as well as foreign language subject curriculum) at the general education level negatively affects the level of efficiency of the teaching process of this subject; 3) In the process of using the foreign language subject curriculum, at the basis of the mistakes manifested in the activity of practical educators, there are reasons, as well as insufficient honest understanding of its essence by these subjects; 4) "System-structure" approach is the most reliable dialectical method of understanding any existing thing, getting to its essence; 5) The dialectical method of the "system-structure" approach regarding the discovery of the essence of the foreign language subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods was not used in theoretical and technological directions; 6) One of the cognitive issues aimed at solving the problem that creates the basis for the manifestations of the error caused by the "gap" regarding the discovery of the essence of the foreign language subject curriculum and the determination of the ways of its application is based on the "system-structural" approach of the "Elements of the Learning Strategies Block" of the Foreign Language Subject Curriculum at the General Education Level interpretation" and our research summary presented in this direction benefits the teaching process of this or that subject.

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